

Temperature-induced microstructure evolution of geopolymer-copper slag composites-implications on high-temperature applications

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Introduction

Many recycling solutions of slag from pyrometallurgical processing of copper ore have been proposed including substitution of natural aggregate and binder phase in concrete, metal recovery etc. Applications taking advantage of the microwave absorption capacity of copper slag have recently been in focus. Our research group is currently investigating the possibility of using geopolymer-copper slag composites as engineered materials for heat generation under microwave irradiation. In this context, a full understanding of the temperature-induced microstructural evolution is fundamental. Hence, this work reports the results from various *in-situ* methods such as optical dilatometry, thermogravimetry in conjunction with differential thermal analyses (TG/DTA) and *in-situ* high temperature X-ray powder diffraction (HT-XRPD). In addition, *ex-situ* analyses using scanning electron microscopy (SEM-EDS) and X-ray powder diffraction (XRPD) were performed following heat treatment in an electrical furnace. The results highlight the recrystallization behavior of the composite and consequent dimensional stability.

Figure1: Micrograph of as-received copper slag.

Figure2: XRPD pattern of the geopolymer without copper slag and copper slag alone.

Results & Discussion

Copper slag

The copper slag is made of a chemically homogeneous vitreous matrix embedding zoned spinel crystals ($(Fe,Mg,Zn)(Cr,Al)_2O_4$), and spherical regions composed of nickel and copper, see Figure3. Iron-rich olivine ($Fe,Mg)_2SiO_4$) is confirmed by XRPD (Figure2).

Figure3: EDS elemental maps of copper slag in cross (polished).

Figure4: HT-XRPD data and RT data following heating at 1090 °C. As-received copper slag is shown for comparison.

Figure5: BE-SEM micrographs of copper slag following thermal treatment at 1064 °C and 1206 °C.

Copper slag shows continuous crystallization of iron oxide phases starting from 680 °C (Figure4). Original iron-rich olivine (fayalite) is no longer detected at 880 °C, probably due to oxidation forming hematite and cristobalite (first visible at this temperature). At 1090 °C, the intensity of cristobalite reflections increases further and enstatite reflections ($MgSiO_3$) appear. The original spinel phase ($Fe,Mg,Zn)(Cr,Al)_2O_4$, hercynite) persists throughout the experiment. Recrystallization results in particles with a shell of iron oxide and a core of embedded newly-formed crystals (Figure5). Large spherical pores are visible at temperatures higher than 1064 °C (Figure5).

Geopolymer-copper slag composite

The copper slag particles are well-adhered to the geopolymer matrix (Figure6a,b). The latter is *per se* a composite, showing embedded residual crystals not reactive in the geopolymerization (Figure6c).

Figure6: Backscattered electron SEM images of composite.

Figure7: Thermal analyses and optical dilatometry of the geopolymer-copper slag composite. Dilatometry of the geopolymer matrix is shown for comparison (discontinuous red line).

The following can be deduced from Figure7 :

- The DTA curve shows a first peak at 98 °C assigned to dehydration. Several major crystallization peaks are observed in the range 690-1100 °C and assigned to devitrification of the copper slag. The broad peak at 1100 °C is accompanied by accelerated oxygen uptake (see TG curve, black continuous line).
- The composite is dimensionally stable up to ca 700 °C (optical dilatometry). A first minor contraction of 0.8% is observed in the range 650-780 (devitrification). A second shrinkage of 1.3% is observed in the range 840-990 % (viscous sintering of the geopolymer matrix). At ca. 1000°C, the composite starts to expand due to expansion of the copper slag (see Figure5).

Conclusions

The composite shows phase and dimensional stability up to ca. 600 °C. The recrystallized composite exhibits only a minor contraction (-2.1%) up to 1000 °. Further work will be dedicated to microwave radiation experiments and mechanical properties (thermal fatigue tests) to fully explore the potential of these materials as microwave susceptors.